

Supplementary Information

Shear-induced Structural Transitions in Confined Nematic Soft Interfaces

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Figure S1. (a) Scanning electron micrograph of the cross-section of a channel-etched glass slide, (b) photograph of the microfluidic channel placed on the microscope in operation, sketches showing (c) the channel design (e) DMOAP coating procedures and (d) 5CB and aqueous phase flow configurations.

a) No functionalization

b) Homogeneous DMOAP surfaces

Figure S2. Polarized optical micrographs showing the LC and water flow in a 20 μm deep microfluidic channel in the case of (a) unmodified and (b) homogeneously DMOAP coated surfaces causing an instability at the LC-aqueous interface. The orientation of the analyzer and polarizers are shown with white double-sided arrows. Scale bar: 200 μm .

Figure S3. The average P_{inlet} values at which the ordering transition of 5CB molecules occurs from Bowser to Dowser state plotted with respect to fabricated channel depths. Error bars are the standard deviations of the independent repeat experiments listed in Table S1.

Figure S4. Fluorescent confocal polarized micrographs of the (a) mid-planes and (b) z-stacks of the 5CB (with 0.01% Nile Red fluorophore) where 5CB and aqueous phase sides were flowing co-currently with the indicated inlet pressures. Polarization directions of the excitation light sources were shown with white marks in the images. Insets in micrographs show the intensity profiles indicated by the same-colored arrows in images. Scale bars: (a) 20 μm , (b) 10 μm .

Figure S5. Polarized optical micrographs of 5CB flowing in hard-interfaced microchannel of 20 μm . Flow is maintained at constant pressures indicated above the images. The orientation of the analyzer and polarizers are shown with white double-sided arrows. Scale bars: 100 μm .

Figure S6. Fluorescent confocal micrographs of Dowser states of the 5CB (with 0.01% Nile Red fluorophore) where the aqueous phase flows in (a) co-current and (b) counter-current. Flow is maintained at pressures indicated above the images. Polarization directions of the excitation light sources were shown with white marks in the images. (c) The intensity profiles are indicated on the right side by the same-colored arrows in the images. Scale bars: (a,b) 10 μm .

Figure S7. Fluorescent confocal micrographs of the (a) Bowser and (b) Dowser states of the 5CB (with 0.01% Nile Red fluorophore) where 5CB flow was maintained at constant indicated pressure and aqueous phase flow was varied as indicated above the images. The last row in (a) and (b) shows the z-stacked micrographs of the three flow conditions where the excitation polarization was along with the flow direction. Co-current flow from right to left was maintained in the channels at indicated inlet pressures. Polarization directions of the excitation light sources were shown with white marks in the images. The intensity profiles are indicated on the right side by the same-colored arrows in the images in the same row. Scale bars: (a,b) mid-plane images: 20 μm , z-stacks: 10 μm .

Figure S8. Fluorescent confocal micrographs of the (a) Bowser and (b) Dowser states of the 5CB (with 0.01% Nile Red fluorophore) where 5CB flow was maintained at constant indicated pressure and aqueous phase flow was varied as indicated above the images. Counter-current flow from right to left was maintained in the channels at indicated inlet pressures. Polarization directions of the excitation light sources were shown with white marks in the images. The intensity profiles are indicated on the right side by the same-colored arrows in the images in the same row. Scale bars: (a,b) 20 μm .

Table S1. The experimental details

Flow Config.	LC Bulk Configuration	Anchoring at LC-Aqueous Interface	Interfacial Shear	Number of Experiments (n)	% Observed Configuration
Co-current	Bowser	Planar	Low	12	83
			High	9	89
		Homeotropic	Low	10	70
			High	8	63
	Dowser	Planar	Low	11	100
			High	8	100
		Homeotropic	Low	10	100
			High	8	100
Counter-current	Bowser	Planar	Low	3	100
			High	3	100
		Homeotropic	Low	4	75
			High	4	75
	Dowser	Planar	Low	3	100
			High	3	100
		Homeotropic	Low	4	75
			High	4	75